

Evaluating Geomasking with MaskMyPy: Privacy–Utility Trade-offs on Synthetic Cologne Microdata

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Abstract—Geographic masking (geomasking) is a family of techniques that modify the spatial coordinates of sensitive point data in order to protect individual privacy while preserving as much analytical utility as possible. This paper applies the open-source Python library MaskMyPy [1] to a synthetic microdata set for the City of Cologne ($n = 10,922$ records) and systematically evaluates eight masking variants: three parameterisations each of Donut masking and Location Swap masking, as well as plain Voronoi masking and Voronoi masking with street-network snapping. Using MaskMyPy’s built-in quality metrics — displacement distance, central drift, nearest-neighbour distance (NND) and NND-delta, Ripley’s K RMSE, and point-level k -anonymity — we conduct a quantitative comparison of information loss and privacy protection across all variants. The analysis reveals a fundamental trade-off: larger displacement ranges improve k -anonymity but inflate information loss, while Voronoi masking with street snapping improves privacy over plain Voronoi at the cost of considerably greater spatial distortion. Within this experimental setup and synthetic Cologne dataset, Location Swap masking at the 200–300 m range achieves the best overall balance, combining the highest k -anonymity satisfaction with comparatively low Ripley’s K RMSE. The paper also reflects critically on the usability of MaskMyPy, its design assumptions, and the limitations encountered — in particular the inability to execute street masking on the full dataset due to an integer overflow error in the underlying NetworkX graph library, the use of a self-referencing population layer, and the single-seed design of the experiment.

Index Terms—geomasking, geoprivacy, spatial microdata, k -anonymity, MaskMyPy, Cologne

I. INTRODUCTION

Empirically working scientists have a sustained interest in individual-level microdata — data that captures attributes and behaviours of specific persons, households, or establishments. When such data additionally carries spatial reference information, for example home addresses or point coordinates, it becomes exceptionally powerful for research: distances to schools, hospitals, pharmacies, or other facilities can be computed; accessibility gradients in rural versus urban settings can be studied; and spatially heterogeneous exposure patterns can be linked to health or educational outcomes [1].

At the same time, spatially referenced microdata presents severe data-protection risks. A set of point coordinates can, in principle, uniquely identify the home address of an individual even when all explicit identifiers have been removed [2]. For this reason, statistical offices and administrative bodies that hold such data have traditionally restricted access to pre-aggregated tables or synthetic area-level statistics, which limits the analytical depth available to researchers.

Geographic masking (geomasking) offers a middle path: the true coordinates of each record are replaced by displaced coordinates, such that re-identification becomes difficult or impossible, while the spatial structure of the data — clustering patterns, distance relationships, neighbourhood compositions — is distorted as little as possible. The key challenge is that these two objectives are inherently in tension: more aggressive masking tends to reduce re-identification risk but degrades the analytical validity of the data, and vice versa [1].

MaskMyPy, introduced by Swanlund and Schuurman [1], is an open-source Python library that operationalises several established geomasking algorithms and, crucially, provides a suite of quantitative metrics to evaluate the resulting information loss and privacy protection. The library thereby makes it possible to systematically compare masking variants and to select the approach that best satisfies a user’s requirements on both dimensions.

This paper applies MaskMyPy to a synthetic Cologne microdata set containing 10,922 georeferenced records, evaluates eight masking variants with MaskMyPy’s full evaluation toolkit, and provides a reasoned assessment of which variant is most suitable for research purposes. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section II provides background on geomasking and the MaskMyPy library. Section III describes the dataset. Section IV documents the masking configuration and evaluation metrics. Section V presents the results. Section VI offers a critical discussion, including limitations. Section VII concludes.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Geographic Masking

Geographic masking is the process of modifying the spatial coordinates of sensitive point locations so that the individuals represented by those locations cannot be identified, while the overall spatial pattern of the data is preserved as faithfully as possible [1]. The concept of *k-anonymity* — the requirement that any individual location be indistinguishable from at least $k - 1$ other plausible locations — has become a widely used formal criterion for privacy protection in this context [2].

The literature distinguishes several families of geomasking methods. *Donut geomasking* [3] randomly displaces each point to a location drawn uniformly from the annular region between an inner and outer radius, guaranteeing a minimum and maximum displacement. *Location swap* [4] replaces the coordinates of each point with those of another point selected within a search radius, thereby preserving the marginal distribution of coordinates while severing attribute-location linkages. *Voronoi masking* snaps each point to the centroid of the Voronoi cell in which it falls, producing a many-to-one mapping that offers deterministic but often limited displacement. *Street masking* [5] uses the OpenStreetMap road network to snap displaced points to reachable network nodes, producing contextually plausible masked locations.

The evaluation of geomasking quality typically spans two dimensions: *information loss*, capturing how much the masked point pattern deviates from the original, and *privacy protection*, capturing how well the masking conceals the true location of each record.

B. The MaskMyPy Library

MaskMyPy is an open-source Python package developed by Swanlund and Schuurman [1] that consolidates geomasking methods and evaluation tools into a unified, user-friendly interface. The library supports the following masking methods: Donut masking, Street masking, Location Swap masking, and Voronoi masking. Each method can be parameterised flexibly, and a special class called the `Atlas` enables batch execution and automatic logging of masking parameters alongside evaluation metrics.

Quality Evaluation Tools in MaskMyPy: MaskMyPy provides the following built-in metrics, accessed via its `analysis` module:

- **Displacement distance** (`analysis.displacement`): Euclidean distance in metres between each original point and its masked counterpart. Summarised as minimum, maximum, median, and mean.
- **Central drift** (`analysis.central_drift`): Euclidean distance between the centroid of the original dataset and the centroid of the masked dataset. A low value indicates that masking has not introduced a systematic directional bias.
- **Nearest-neighbour distance and NND-delta** (`analysis.nnd`, `analysis.nnd_delta`): For each

point, the distance to its nearest neighbour within the same layer. The delta quantifies the per-layer change in NND statistics (masked minus sensitive), measuring how much the local point spacing has changed.

- **Ripley’s K function and RMSE** (`analysis.ripleys_k`, `analysis.ripley_rmse`): Ripley’s K is a spatial statistic that measures clustering as a function of distance. The RMSE between the K curve of the masked data and that of the sensitive data captures how well the global clustering structure is preserved.
- **k -anonymity** (`analysis.k_anonymity`, `analysis.summarize_k`): For each masked point, the number of candidate true locations (addresses in the population layer) that fall within a radius equal to the displacement distance. A masked point satisfies k -anonymity at threshold k if at least k candidates exist within this radius.

The `Atlas.as_df()` method consolidates all metrics into a single comparison table, making cross-variant evaluation straightforward. This design represents a considerable usability advantage over approaches that require custom-coded evaluation pipelines.

III. DATA

The analysis is based on a synthetic microdata set representing individuals in the City of Cologne, Germany. The dataset comprises 10,922 georeferenced point records, each carrying the following attributes: a unique identifier (`id`), district (`district`), gender (`gender`), age (`age`), a continuous noise-level exposure value (`noise_level`), a binary flag for sleep disorder (`sleep_disorder`), and projected spatial coordinates (`geometry`) in the EPSG:25832 reference system (UTM Zone 32N).

All 10,922 records were treated as sensitive and included in the masking process; no filtering by attribute was performed. Following MaskMyPy’s recommended setup, both the *population layer* (used for k -anonymity computation) and the *address layer* (used as candidate swap targets for Location Swap masking) were set to the original sensitive layer itself. This configuration is a pragmatic approximation that avoids the need for a separate, comprehensive address register but has implications for the resulting k -anonymity values, which are discussed in Section VI.

IV. METHODS

A. Masking Configuration

Eight masking variants were applied using MaskMyPy’s `Atlas` class with a fixed random seed of 42 to ensure reproducibility. The variants and their parameters are as follows.

Donut masking was applied with three displacement ranges: 50–100 m, 100–200 m, and 200–300 m. Donut masking draws a random angle and a random radius drawn uniformly from the specified annular region, guaranteeing

that every displaced point lies at least `low` metres and at most `high` metres from its original position.

Voronoi masking was applied in two variants: plain Voronoi (`snap_to_streets = False`) and Voronoi with street-network snapping (`snap_to_streets = True`). The latter additionally routes displaced points to the nearest node on the OSM street network, increasing effective displacement and concentrating multiple original points onto shared network nodes, which improves k -anonymity.

Location Swap masking was applied with three displacement ranges: 50–100 m, 100–200 m, and 200–300 m. For each point, the algorithm searches within the specified radius for a swap partner from the address layer and exchanges coordinates.

Street masking was attempted but could not be executed on the full dataset due to a runtime error. When applying MaskMyPy’s street mask to larger subsets of the dataset, an `OverflowError: int too large to convert to float` was encountered. Street masking relies on expanding shortest-path searches on an OpenStreetMap-derived street network to build a pool of candidate nodes within a distance cutoff. For certain points present in the first 3,000 records but absent in the first 2,000, the reachable street-network component is too small or effectively disconnected for the algorithm to satisfy its target candidate pool. As a result, the implementation repeatedly increases the Dijkstra cutoff distance until it exceeds the floating-point representable range, triggering the overflow within NetworkX’s cutoff comparison. This limitation is discussed further in Section VI-D.

B. Evaluation Framework

All eight variants were evaluated using MaskMyPy’s `analysis` module, computing displacement summaries, central drift, NND summaries, NND-delta, Ripley’s K RMSE, k -anonymity distributions, and k -satisfaction rates at thresholds $k \geq 5$, $k \geq 10$, and $k \geq 25$. All results were aggregated with `Atlas.as_df()` and exported for analysis.

V. RESULTS

A. Overview: Spatial Distribution of Masked Variants

Figure 1 shows the spatial distribution of all eight masked datasets alongside the original sensitive data. All variants broadly preserve the footprint of the Cologne settlement pattern. Donut-masked datasets are visually close to the original at the 50–100 m range and show progressive diffusion at larger ranges. Location Swap datasets appear qualitatively similar to the sensitive data due to coordinate exchange but show some outlier points at the 50–100 m range where unmasked points ($n = 3,244$) retain their original positions. Voronoi-masked points cluster tightly, reflecting the centroid-snapping mechanism; street-snapped Voronoi data shows slightly higher spread.

B. Displacement Distance

Figure 2 shows the displacement distributions across all variants. Table I reports the corresponding summary statistics.

Donut masking strictly respects its parameterised displacement bounds, confirming correct algorithm implementation. Plain Voronoi masking produces a median displacement of only 21.9 m — the smallest of all variants — reflecting its deterministic centroid-snapping logic in a densely settled urban area. Street-snapping increases the median Voronoi displacement to 55.4 m and introduces extreme outliers above 600 m in areas where the nearest reachable street node is distant. Location Swap variants have minimum displacements of 0 m because points for which no suitable swap partner exists within the search radius are left in place; this is particularly marked for the 50–100 m variant, where 3,244 records (29.7%) were unmasked.

C. Central Drift

Central drift measures the shift of the global centroid induced by masking. Figure 3 illustrates the values across all variants.

The three Donut variants produce central drift values of approximately 13 m — remarkably stable across displacement ranges and substantially lower than all other variants. This confirms that donut masking’s uniform random direction preserves the mean position of the point cloud. Voronoi variants produce moderate drift (22 m and 38 m for plain and snapped, respectively). The Location Swap 50–100 m variant produces the highest central drift of 92 m, attributable to the large number of unmasked records that remain at their true positions and distort the centroid relative to the displaced subset.

D. Nearest-Neighbour Distance and NND-Delta

Figure 4 shows NND summary statistics (minimum, mean, and maximum) across all variants relative to the sensitive baseline. Figure 5 shows the NND-delta, i.e. the change in NND statistics from the sensitive to the masked data.

The sensitive dataset has a mean NND of 53.2 m. Donut masking increases the mean NND with increasing displacement range (66.2 m at 50–100 m, 71.9 m at 100–200 m, and 75.4 m at 200–300 m), indicating progressive local dispersion of points. Voronoi masking dramatically reduces the mean NND (19.7 m plain, 13.3 m snapped) because multiple original points snap to the same Voronoi centroid or street node, creating apparent near-zero neighbour distances. Location Swap variants also reduce the mean NND (42.7 m, 30.7 m, and 29.4 m for the three ranges, respectively), since swapping coordinates between nearby points concentrates them relative to the original spacing.

Fig. 1. Spatial distribution of the sensitive dataset and all eight masked variants over the Cologne study area. Each panel plots 10,922 points in projected coordinates (EPSG:25832). Donut variants (red shades) show increasing diffusion with displacement range. Voronoi variants (orange) concentrate points at centroid positions. Location Swap variants (green) preserve global footprint while displacing within neighbourhood bounds.

E. Ripley's K Function and RMSE

Ripley's K function measures the cumulative density of point pairs within increasing distance thresholds, providing a global characterisation of clustering across spatial scales.

Figure 6 plots the K curves for all variants against the sensitive baseline, and Table II ranks variants by Ripley's K RMSE.

Location Swap masking at 50–100 m achieves the lowest

Fig. 2. Boxplot of displacement distances (in metres) for all eight masking variants. Donut variants exhibit narrow, controlled distributions bounded by their specified annular ranges. Voronoi (plain) produces a left-skewed distribution concentrated below 100 m with a long right tail. Voronoi Snapped introduces substantial outliers exceeding 600 m. Location Swap variants show broader, right-skewed distributions within their respective upper bounds, with minimum displacements of 0 m where suitable swap partners could not be found.

TABLE I
DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY STATISTICS (METRES) FOR ALL MASKING VARIANTS.

Variant	Min	Median	Mean	Max
Donut 50–100	50.00	75.04	75.08	100.00
Donut 100–200	100.00	150.09	150.15	200.00
Donut 200–300	200.00	250.09	250.15	300.00
Voronoi	0.00	21.86	28.23	252.77
Voronoi Snapped	0.11	55.43	74.59	681.48
Swap 50–100	0.00	67.52	54.27	99.88
Swap 100–200	0.00	153.15	146.13	199.92
Swap 200–300	0.00	252.78	244.80	299.95

TABLE II
RIPLEY’S K RMSE FOR ALL MASKING VARIANTS, RANKED FROM LOWEST (BEST) TO HIGHEST (WORST) INFORMATION LOSS.

Variant	Ripley’s K RMSE
Location Swap 50–100	28,410
Location Swap 200–300	61,133
Donut 50–100	458,152
Voronoi	510,934
Location Swap 100–200	1,357,768
Donut 100–200	1,484,354
Donut 200–300	3,156,066
Voronoi Snapped	6,920,770

RMSE by a wide margin (28,410), indicating near-perfect preservation of the global spatial clustering structure. This is expected: by exchanging coordinates between nearby points rather than displacing them randomly, Location

Swap masking preserves inter-point distances and consequently the K -function profile. Location Swap at 200–300 m also performs well (61,133), as partners drawn from a 200–300 m radius remain close neighbours. Donut masking at

Fig. 3. Central drift (metres) by masking variant. Low values indicate that the masked point cloud preserves the mean spatial position of the sensitive data. Donut variants achieve the lowest central drift (approximately 13 m regardless of range), while Location Swap at the 50–100 m range produces the highest drift (92 m), driven by the large share of unmasked points whose original positions create an unbalanced distribution of displaced coordinates.

Fig. 4. Nearest-neighbour distance (NND) summary statistics for the sensitive dataset and all masked variants. The sensitive dataset has a mean NND of 53.2 m. Donut variants increase the mean NND (i.e. locally spread points further apart), while Voronoi and Location Swap variants decrease it (i.e. concentrate points closer together), reflecting the aggregating and centroid-snapping mechanisms of those methods.

50–100 m is third (458,152) but an order of magnitude worse than the best Location Swap variants. Voronoi Snapped produces the worst RMSE (6,920,770), reflecting the substantial spatial distortion introduced by snapping to a coarse street network.

F. k -Anonymity

Summary Statistics: Table III reports k -anonymity summary statistics, and Figure 7 shows the proportion of points satisfying $k \geq 5$, $k \geq 10$, and $k \geq 25$ for each variant.

k -Anonymity Satisfaction Curves: Figure 8 shows the k -satisfaction curve for each variant, plotting the proportion of points satisfying threshold k across all integer values of k .

The results demonstrate a clear and consistent pattern: k -anonymity satisfaction increases with displacement range within each masking family. Plain Voronoi masking fails entirely at $k \geq 5$ (satisfaction = 0.000), because the small, deterministic displacements to Voronoi centroids enclose too few candidate population points. Street-snapping raises Voronoi’s $k \geq 5$ satisfaction to 15.6%, still far below the

Fig. 5. NND-delta (masked minus sensitive) by variant, showing minimum, mean, and maximum change in nearest-neighbour distance. Positive mean NND-delta values (Donut variants) indicate local point dispersion; negative values (Voronoi and Location Swap variants) indicate local clustering in the masked data. The Donut 200–300 m variant shows the largest positive max-delta (186.6 m), while Voronoi (plain) shows the largest negative max-delta (−92.2 m), reflecting strong aggregation of points onto centroid positions.

Fig. 6. Ripley’s K function curves for the sensitive dataset (orange) and each masked variant (blue), with simulation envelopes. A smaller gap between the two curves indicates better preservation of the global clustering structure. The Location Swap 50–100 m variant (top right) shows near-perfect curve alignment, while Voronoi Snapped (bottom right) exhibits the greatest divergence.

displacement-based methods. Location Swap 200–300 m achieves the highest k -satisfaction across all thresholds ($k \geq 5$: 91.9%, $k \geq 10$: 67.5%, $k \geq 25$: 15.1%), marginally outperforming Donut 200–300 m ($k \geq 5$: 84.4%, $k \geq 10$: 57.9%, $k \geq 25$: 11.9%).

Voronoi: Effect of Street Snapping on k -Anonymity: Figure 9 compares the displacement density distributions

of plain Voronoi and Voronoi-Snapped, illustrating the mechanism through which snapping improves k -anonymity. The plain Voronoi variant (blue) is concentrated at very small displacements; the snapped variant (orange) shifts the distribution rightward, enabling more population-layer candidates to fall within the displacement radius.

Quantitatively, plain Voronoi exhibits a near-zero correla-

TABLE III
 k -ANONYMITY SUMMARY STATISTICS AND SATISFACTION RATES AT THREE THRESHOLDS.

Variant	k min	k med	k mean	k max	$k \geq 5$	$k \geq 10$	$k \geq 25$
Donut 50–100	1	2	2.43	14	0.107	0.003	0.000
Donut 100–200	1	5	5.81	29	0.532	0.167	0.001
Donut 200–300	1	11	13.13	60	0.844	0.579	0.119
Voronoi	1	1	1.00	6	0.000	0.000	0.000
Voronoi Snapped	1	2	2.96	48	0.156	0.039	0.004
Swap 50–100	1	3	2.96	14	0.195	0.008	0.000
Swap 100–200	1	6	7.18	36	0.681	0.250	0.002
Swap 200–300	1	13	14.91	65	0.919	0.675	0.151

Fig. 7. k -anonymity satisfaction rates at thresholds $k \geq 5$, $k \geq 10$, and $k \geq 25$ for all masking variants. Larger displacement ranges consistently improve k -satisfaction across all method families. Location Swap 200–300 m and Donut 200–300 m are the two highest-performing variants. Plain Voronoi masking fails to satisfy $k \geq 5$ for any point in the dataset.

tion between displacement and k -anonymity ($r = -0.022$), indicating that larger displacements do not reliably increase the number of candidate locations in this deterministic setting. Voronoi Snapped achieves $r = 0.734$, confirming that street snapping creates a meaningful positive relationship between displacement magnitude and privacy protection.

G. Comprehensive Comparison Table

Table IV consolidates all evaluation metrics into a single overview, replicating the output of MaskMyPy’s `Atlas.as_df()` method.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Privacy–Utility Trade-off

The results confirm the fundamental trade-off between privacy protection and spatial utility that is well-established in the geomasking literature [1, 2]. Across all three masking families, larger displacement ranges consistently improve k -anonymity at the cost of greater information loss as measured by NND-delta and Ripley’s K RMSE. The optimal operating point along this trade-off depends on the specific research context.

For applications in which spatial clustering at fine scales (sub-kilometre) is the primary analytical interest, the Donut

family offers a well-controlled trade-off: Donut 100–200 m achieves $k \geq 5$ satisfaction of 53.2% with a Ripley RMSE of 1.48 million, while Donut 50–100 m achieves only 10.7% satisfaction with lower RMSE. Neither variant satisfies conventional privacy thresholds (e.g. $k \geq 5$ for all records) at the 50–100 m and 100–200 m ranges.

B. Which Method Is More Suitable for Research?

Considering both dimensions of quality simultaneously, **Location Swap 200–300 m** emerges as the preferred variant within the present synthetic Cologne test setup. It achieves the highest k -anonymity satisfaction of all variants ($k \geq 5$: 91.9%, $k \geq 10$: 67.5%), while maintaining the second-lowest Ripley’s K RMSE overall (61,133) — a value that is more than an order of magnitude below the equivalent-range Donut variant (3.16 million). This combination is made possible by Location Swap’s coordinate-exchange mechanism, which preserves the relative spacing between points and thus the overall clustering signature, while achieving substantial displacement.

Donut 200–300 m is a credible alternative if a method that guarantees a strict minimum displacement of 200 m for every point is required. Its Ripley RMSE is substantially higher, but its k -anonymity satisfaction (84.4% at $k \geq 5$)

Fig. 8. k -anonymity satisfaction curves: for each threshold k (x-axis), the proportion of masked points satisfying k -anonymity is shown (y-axis). The curves reveal a clear ordering by displacement range within each method family. Plain Voronoi (red) falls immediately to zero after $k = 1$, indicating negligible privacy protection. Donut 200–300 m (dark green) and Location Swap 200–300 m (grey) achieve the highest and most persistent satisfaction across all thresholds.

Fig. 9. Kernel density of displacement distances for Voronoi (no street snap, blue) and Voronoi + street snapping (orange). Street snapping shifts the displacement distribution towards larger values, increasing the number of candidate locations within the displacement radius and thereby improving k -anonymity satisfaction. The correlation between displacement and k -anonymity rises from $r = -0.022$ (plain Voronoi) to $r = 0.734$ (Voronoi Snapped), confirming that the snapping mechanism is the primary driver of improved privacy.

is close to the Location Swap equivalent. For research that emphasises guaranteed individual-level displacement rather than aggregate-level clustering fidelity, Donut masking may be preferable.

TABLE IV
FULL QUANTITATIVE COMPARISON OF ALL MASKING VARIANTS ACROSS ALL EVALUATION METRICS.

Variant	C.Drift	D.Med	D.Mean	NND Δ mean	Rip.RMSE	k med	k mean	$k \geq 5$	$k \geq 10$
Donut 50–100	13.1	75.0	75.1	+13.0	458k	2.0	2.43	0.107	0.003
Donut 100–200	13.2	150.1	150.2	+18.7	1,484k	5.0	5.81	0.532	0.167
Donut 200–300	13.4	250.1	250.2	+22.2	3,156k	11.0	13.13	0.844	0.579
Voronoi	22.4	21.9	28.2	−33.5	511k	1.0	1.00	0.000	0.000
Voronoi Snap.	37.6	55.4	74.6	−39.9	6,921k	2.0	2.96	0.156	0.039
Swap 50–100	92.0	67.5	54.3	−10.5	28k	3.0	2.96	0.195	0.008
Swap 100–200	28.8	153.2	146.1	−22.5	1,358k	6.0	7.18	0.681	0.250
Swap 200–300	45.4	252.8	244.8	−23.8	61k	13.0	14.91	0.919	0.675

Plain Voronoi masking is not suitable for research use in the present context. Its k -anonymity satisfaction is zero at all tested thresholds, meaning no point in the masked dataset satisfies $k \geq 5$, and its NND-delta indicates severe local over-aggregation. Voronoi Snapped partially addresses the privacy deficit but at the cost of very high Ripley RMSE and highly variable displacements, including large outliers.

C. User-Friendliness of MaskMyPy

MaskMyPy is notably user-friendly for a research-grade geomasking tool. Installation via pip requires a single command (`pip install maskmypy[extra]`). The `Atlas` class provides a declarative, configuration-driven interface: the user specifies a sensitive `GeoDataFrame`, a population layer, and a sequence of masking calls, and the `Atlas` automatically logs parameters, execution times, and all evaluation metrics into a single tabular summary. This substantially reduces the evaluation overhead compared to custom coding.

The `analysis` module exposes a clean functional API: `analysis.displacement()`, `analysis.central_drift()`, `analysis.nnd()`, `analysis.ripleys_k()`, and `analysis.k_anonymity()` each operate on a pair of `GeoDataFrames` and return structured outputs that integrate naturally with standard Python data science libraries (`pandas`, `geopandas`, `matplotlib`). The `graph_ripleyresult()` convenience function renders publication-ready K -function plots with simulation envelopes.

Where user-friendliness is reduced is in the handling of edge cases and dependency management. The `voronoi_snapped` variant requires `OSMnx` and took more time than Donut variants to execute on the 10,922-point dataset. Street masking is even more demanding and, in the present experiment, unexecutable due to the overflow error described above. Documentation for these failure modes is sparse. The assumption that users supply a population layer that is denser than their sensitive layer is not enforced by the library and can silently produce misleading k -anonymity results when violated (as occurred here, where population = sensitive layer).

D. Limitations

Several limitations of this analysis warrant explicit acknowledgement.

Population layer self-referencing. Both the population layer and the address layer were set to the original sensitive dataset. In MaskMyPy’s k -anonymity calculation, the population layer defines the set of candidate true locations within which masked points must be distinguishable. When the population and sensitive layers are identical, k -anonymity is computed against the original point positions themselves, rather than against a separate, comprehensive register of addresses. This constitutes an upward bias on k -anonymity for the Location Swap variants (since the swap targets are drawn from the same layer) and a downward bias for methods that displace points away from the original cloud (since the candidates are concentrated at original positions rather than distributed across the study area). A proper deployment should use a comprehensive address register as the population layer.

Single-seed evaluation. All masking variants were executed with a fixed random seed of 42 to ensure reproducibility. This makes the present comparison internally consistent, but it does not capture the variation that can arise across repeated runs of randomized masking algorithms. As Swanlund and Schuurman [1] note, mask performance can vary materially due solely to randomization, especially when methods are compared using a single execution. A stronger follow-up study should therefore repeat the analysis across multiple random seeds and compare the stability of the method rankings.

Street masking unavailable. As documented above, street masking could not be applied to the full dataset due to an `OverflowError` in NetworkX’s Dijkstra-based shortest-path expansion. The error arises when certain points have access to only a small, effectively disconnected street-network component. For these points, MaskMyPy’s internal mechanism repeatedly inflates the cutoff distance until it exceeds the representable float range, triggering the overflow. This is a bug in MaskMyPy’s street masking implementation and prevents a comparison with this theoretically attractive method.

Deterministic Voronoi limitations. Plain Voronoi masking is fully deterministic given a fixed sensitive dataset and Voronoi tessellation, and produces small displacements in densely settled urban areas where Voronoi cells are compact. The resulting near-zero k -anonymity is not a limitation of the concept but of the specific dataset geometry: in areas with sparse settlement or coarser spatial resolution, Voronoi cells would be larger and displacements correspondingly greater.

Synthetic data. The dataset used is synthetic and was generated to mimic the statistical properties of Cologne microdata. While this enables open analysis and reproducibility, it means that the results may not translate directly to real administrative microdata, which may have different spatial clustering structures, attribute distributions, or boundary effects.

AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

This manuscript is a seminar research report and has not undergone peer review. The associated Zenodo DOI for this release is 10.5281/zenodo.19386882. The public release accompanying this report contains the manuscript PDF, LaTeX source, bibliography, and figure files. The analysis scripts and synthetic input data are not included in the public release at this stage. If a fuller reproducibility package is prepared later, the workflow description, software versions, and any shareable supplementary materials can be archived separately, subject to supervisor approval and licensing considerations.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper has applied MaskMyPy to a 10,922-record synthetic Cologne microdata set and evaluated eight masking variants using MaskMyPy’s comprehensive quality evaluation toolkit. The principal findings are as follows.

Regarding spatial quality after applying information loss methods, **Location Swap masking preserves the global clustering structure most faithfully**, as measured by Ripley’s K RMSE: the 50–100 m and 200–300 m variants achieve RMSE values of 28,410 and 61,133 respectively, compared to hundreds of thousands to millions for equivalent Donut and Voronoi variants. Donut masking introduces progressively more distortion as displacement range increases, and Voronoi Snapped produces the worst spatial fidelity of all variants.

Regarding spatial quality after applying anonymisation methods (privacy), **Location Swap 200–300 m and Donut 200–300 m achieve the highest k -anonymity**, with $k \geq 5$ satisfaction of 91.9% and 84.4% respectively. Plain Voronoi provides essentially no protection; Voronoi Snapped provides modest improvement.

On balance, **Location Swap 200–300 m is the preferred variant within the present experimental setup** for research use on the synthetic Cologne dataset. It achieves the highest privacy protection while incurring far lower information loss than the equivalent Donut variant,

offering the best resolution of the inherent privacy–utility trade-off in this study. Donut 200–300 m is a suitable alternative where guaranteed minimum displacement for every individual record is required.

MaskMyPy is a well-designed and accessible library that substantially lowers the barrier to applying and evaluating geographic masks. Its `Atlas` class and `analysis` module cover the full evaluation pipeline in a coherent and reproducible manner. Critical shortcomings include the street masking overflow bug, the high computational cost of network-based operations, and the absence of enforcement or guidance for the population-layer assumption. Future work should address these issues, repeat the comparison across multiple random seeds, and extend evaluation to real administrative datasets with verified address registers.

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